

Ayurveda Interpretation of Kalpana w.s.r to Sneha Kalpana

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. Introduction

Kalpana is Ayurveda terminology used for various types of drug preparation, this term is also used for types of food preparation as Ahara Kalpana. Ashtanga Hrudaya also explains the term Kalpana in Uttarasthana. The processing of medicinal substances is called Bhesaja kalpa while Ahara kalpa indicates the processing of food and management of the body is called Kaya kalpa. The Ayurveda drugs are prepared from various sources including materials obtained from plants, metals, minerals, and marine and animal products. (1-5) The consideration of the concept of Kalpana helps to achieve the best possible drug formulation in terms of efficacy, safety, and palatability. The processing of plant materials as five basic methods is called Panchvidh kashaya kalpana which includes Swrasa, Kalka, Kwatha, Phanta, and Hima.

Sneha Kalpana is defined as the pharmaceutical process where the fat soluble and water soluble active principles are extracted from the basic ingredients into the Sneha. It is a procedure to prepare oleaginous medicine from substances like Kalka and Dravya. They are prepared in specific proportions by subjecting them to uniform heating patterns and duration to fulfill certain pharmaceutical parameters as per the requirement of therapeutics. Most of the Ayurvedic treatments and therapeutics are aimed at maintaining Jatharagni which is responsible for the maintenance of health and Sneha is considered the best one to stimulate Jatharagni. 5 This process or method ensures absorption of active therapeutic principles of the ingredients in two different solvents i.e. water and fat and also some chemical constituents which are soluble in other different Medias like Kanji, Gomutra, etc.

AIM&OBJECTIVES:- To review Sneha Kalpana from Ayurvedic Texts

MATERIAL Literature review from Samhita, Journals, Websites

METHODS Conceptual study Literature

Review: KALPANA

2. Principles of pharmaceutical processing (Bheshaja Kalpa)

Sneha Kalpana is defined as the pharmaceutical process where the fat soluble and water soluble active principles are extracted from the basic ingredients into the Sneha. It is a procedure to prepare oleaginous medicine from substances like Kalka and Dravya. They are prepared in specific proportions by subjecting them to uniform heating patterns and duration to fulfill certain pharmaceutical parameters as per the requirement of therapeutics. Most of the Ayurvedic treatments and therapeutics are aimed at maintaining Jatharagni which is responsible for the maintenance of health and Sneha is considered the best one to stimulate Jatharagni. 5 This process or method ensures absorption of active therapeutic principles of the ingredients in two different solvents i.e. water and fat and also some chemical constituents which are soluble in other different Medias like Kanji, Gomutra, etc.

Pradhanasya Kalpana This concept gives importance to the ingredient of a compound that possesses superior and prominent properties among many substances of similar properties. Compound with Prakrushta Guna is kept as the chief ingredient and formulation is prepared accordingly.

Pradhanena Kalpana Substances belong to a particular group designated based on the important or Pradhana Dravya, for example, substances related to milk are termed as Ksheera Varga since milk is put on importance. Ashtanga Hridaya in Dravadravya Vijnaniyaadhyaya and Annaswaroopa Vijnana Adhyaya, etc. explored the concept of this Kalpana. In classical Ayurveda texts, some Aushadhi yoga is named based on their property of being Pradhanadravya.

Guna Kalpana These formulations are based on the concept of qualities since Guna indicates quality or attribute. Kalpana based on different qualities of an object is called Guna Kalpana. Guna Kalpana is related to the compounds that are attributes of some Karma even though not included under that particular Guna group in Ayurveda.

Lesha Kalpana Lesha is used for a small portion, here few topics are not explored due to their hugeness, and such topics are elaborated as a concise part under the heading of Lesha Kalpana. Vagbhata concisely described the superiority of Karshya over Sthaulya; Acharya Arunadatta mentioned reasons for the same. Here it is mentioned that Sthoulya is

SNEHA YONI

Sneha is derived from two sources, Sthavara and Jangama. Sthavara Sneha- Includes Sarshapa, Tila, Priyala, Vibheetaki, Danti, Harithaki, Eranda, Madhuka, Kusumbha, Bilwa, Shigru etc. Jangama Sneha- Includes Mansa, Majja, Vasa, etc. of quadruped animals, birds and fishes. Sarpi, Majja, Vasa and Taila are the Sneha Chathushtayaas. Among these sarpi is considered the best one, because of its power to assimilate the properties of the ingredients added to it without losing its properties.

CLASSIFICATION OF SNEHA KALPANA

1. Based on the combination of Sneh as

- a. Yamaka- Combination of Ghritha and Taila.
- b. Trivrut- Combination of Ghritha, Taila, and Vasa.
- c. Mahasneha- Combination of all the four Snehas.

2. Based on the Nature of Media

- a) Ghritha Kalpa
- b) Taila Kalpa
- c) Vasa Kalpa
- d) Majja Kalpa

3. Based on the stages of Paka

- a. Ama Paka
- b. Mridu Paka
- c. Madhya Paka
- d. Khara Paka
- e. Dagdha Paka

4. Based on the types of utility

- a. Pana
- b. Savasana
- c. Abhyanga

d. Shirobasti

e. Uttarabasti

f. Nasya

g. Karna Purana

h. Dharan

Ghritha murchana

Ghritha of 756 gm, haritaki, vibhitaki, Amalaki, musta, haridra, and bheejapooraka each measuring 1 pala (48 gm), and 3.024 ml (4 paratha) of water. This is processed till the froth and waves disappear. This is said to be free from Ama Dosha.

Tila taila murchana

1 part of tila taila, 1 part of water and 1/16 parts of manjishta, haridra, musta, lodra, nalika, Amalaki, harutaki, vibhitaki, ketaki, vatankura, hriberi. This is cooked on fire till the water content evaporates. Essential ingredients of Sneha Kalpana: There are generally four essential components required for the preparation of medicated Sneha. They are as follows.

1. Kalka- If the drugs are wet, they should be pounded in Khalva Yantra till they become paste form. If the drugs are dry, then a fine powder should be prepared out of it and the required amount of water is added to obtain a paste form. If the quantity of Kalka is not specified, it should be taken 1/4th of Sneha Dravyas.
2. Sneha- Oleaginous substances are used in this preparation. In that Ghritha and Taila are the prime constituents of Sneha Kalpana. An oleaginous substance acts as a medium for fat-soluble active principles and a carrier of water-soluble principles. If the quantity is not specified, it should be 4 times that of Kalka.
3. Dravadravya- It is taken 4 times to that of Sneha. Dravadravyas can be water, Swarasa, Milk, Curd, or any other liquid preparations.
4. Gandha dravyas- Sugandhi Dravyas like Ela, Lavanga, Karpura, Kasturi, etc. are added in the end state to render fragrance to the Sneha, especially Taila.

POORVA KARMA Collection of Dravyas:-Dravyas are collected from the appropriate habitat and kala as mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics since they do have many active principles in that particular

time. The Jangama Dravyas are collected from strong animals and their milk, urine, etc. should be collected only after the complete digestion of food. After collecting, the drugs should be washed thoroughly to remove the physical impurities.

Selection of Patra:-Vessels selected should not react with the ingredients of the Sneha Paka. Usually, vessels made out of iron, copper, earthen vessels, and Varthaloha (Panchaloha) were used during ancient times. Now a -day's stainless steel vessels and tin-coated copper vessels have been used for various preparations in many pharmacies. The vessel must be strong enough to withstand the stages of temperature. It should be wide-mouthed with proper depth to avoid spilling of oil while processing. After selecting the vessel, it should be cleaned thoroughly, sterilized, and dried properly.

Selection of Sneha:-If the Taila to be used is not specified, then Tila Taila should be taken. If Ghritha to be used is not specified, then Goghrita should be used. Among Jangama Yoni, Goghrita is considered as the best, and among Sthavara yoni, Tila Taila is considered the best¹⁴ Quantity of Sneha Dravya:-Sneha Dravya are to be taken four times to that of kalka unless or otherwise specified.¹⁵ Kalka: A green or dry drug should be converted into paste form by rubbing or grinding with or without the addition of water and this is called Kalka. Specific rules in the selection of Kalka Dravya. Only Dravyas are mentioned for Sneha Kalpana, then Kalka of the same drugs should be taken. If only Kwatha Dravyas are given in a Sneha preparation then Kalka of the same drugs is added. When Kalka is not indicated or restricted, there Sneha may be prepared without Kalka. If Pushpa Kalka is indicated in Sneha preparation, it should be taken 1/8th quantity of sneha.

SNEHA PAKA SIDDHI LAKSHANA

The desired color, odor, and taste of ingredients become appreciable when Sneha Paka is completed. When Sneha Paka completes, the following confirmative tests can be observed.

1. Sneha Kalka attains perfect wick shape when rolled between two fingers.
2. There should not be any sound when a part of Sneha Kalka is put on fire.
3. Foam appears in Taila Paka (Phenodgama); on the contrary, it subsides in Ghritha Paka (Phenashanti)
4. Gandha, varna, and rasa of the drugs added to individual Sneha are obtained.

PASCHAT KARMA

Preservation Ghritha must be preserved in a wide-mouthed, air-tight glass container or mud pot, and Tailas are usually preserved in glass bottles with narrow mouths.

DISCUSSION

Sneha Kalpana is an important preparation that is used in Ayurvedic treatment as this is a more stable, compatible, and popular dosage form. This is an easy and regularly used dosage form as this reduces oxidation and increases the bio-availability of the processed drugs in it. Kalka: wet drugs are added in Kalka form as this increases the instance of releasing the active principles into Sneha. In the case of dry drugs, powder is prepared and Kalka is obtained as this is helpful in the loosening of the compound in it and assessing the Paka Lakshana in it 1/4th of Kalka is usually added for getting a quality Sneha. According to Acharya Sharangadhara when Kalka is prepared out of flowers 1/8th Sneha has to be taken this may be because the flowers are releasing their active principles easily as they are very soft. According to Bhaishajya Ratnavali always a Murchita Sneha can be used. He mentions the order of adding the ingredients that are Sneha, Kalka, and Kwatha (Drava Dravyas). Usually, Gandha Dravyas are added at last only because the aromatic active principles present in it are volatile. Always it should be maintained with mild fire since it is difficult to calculate the Paka Lakshana correctly. Different times for the preparation like 1 day, 2 days, 3 days, 5 days, and 12 days are mentioned for the preparation of Sneha to get the active principles in total into Sneha and also it is been mentioned concerning the hardness of the ingredient which releases the chemical constituents slowly. Shabdha heena agni nikshipta (absence of sound when subjected to fire) indicates the absence of water content in the Sneha and vice versa. In Sneha Paka occurrence of phenodgama (presence of foam) in taila and Phenashanti (Absence of foam) in Ghrita is normal. It is one of the most frequently used dosage forms which can be given in Manasa Rogas also as fat can pass through the blood-brain barriers.

Reference

1. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, Revised by Charaka and Dridabala with Ayurveda Deepika Commentary of Chakrapanidatta, Edited by Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji, Varanasi; Chowkambha Sanskrit Samsthana – 4 th Edition. 2001, T.pg: 7
2. Sharma Hemaraja Pandit, Satyapala Bhishakacharya, "Kashyapa Samhitha", Vidhyotinitika Yukta, Vrdha Jeevaka Vasty Prathisamskartha, 1sted, Varanasi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series, 1953.
3. Sri Tarka vachaspati Taranath, "Vachaspatyam"(A Comprehensive Sanskrit Dictionary), Vol 3, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series, 1970.
4. Sri Bhavamisra, Bhavaprakasa Nighantu, Commentary by Prof.K.C.Chunekar, Edited by Dr.G.S.Pandey, Revised edition-2010, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy.

5. Sushruta, Sushruta Samhita, with Nibandhasangraha commentary of Nyayachandrikapanjika Dalhanacharya of Gayadas acharya and on Nidanasthana, Edited by jadavjiTrikamji Acharya and Narayan Ram Acharya, re-print 2012, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan.
6. Sharangadharacharya's "Sharangadhar a Samhita", with Adhamalla's „Dipika“ and Kasirama's „Gudantha Dipika“ commentaries, Varanasi, Krishnadas Academy, Reprint 2000.
7. http://www.ccras.nic.in/content/panchavidha-kashaya_kalpana-pharmaceutics-ayurveda accessed on 12/02/2022. The Ayurvedic Formulary of India. Govt. of India, New Delhi: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare; 1978. pp. 1-120. Anonymous.
8. Caraka, „Caraka Samhita“, author Sutra Sthaana. Vol. 1. Varanasi (India): Choukhambha Sanskrita SanSthaana; 1984. p. 126.
9. Caraka, „Caraka Samhita“, author. Cikitsa Sthaana. 3. Vol. 1. Varanasi (India): Choukhambha Sanskrita SanSthaana; 1984. p. 31.
10. Sharangadhara, Chandra Moorthy P Himasagara, Sharangadhara Samhita, choukambha Sanskrit series, Edition -2010, page- 201.
11. Lochan Kanji, Shri Ambika Datta Shastri Vaidhya, Ratnavali, Bhaishajya Chowkambha Sanskrit Sansthan, volume -1, Reprint 2016, Page no. 366.